

Prevalence of Catatonic Symptoms in Postpartum Psychosis

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Abstract:

Background: Postpartum psychosis is a severe psychiatric disorder that affects women shortly after childbirth. Catatonia, characterized by motor abnormalities and behavioral disturbances, is a potential but under-researched component of postpartum psychosis. Understanding the prevalence and clinical implications of catatonic symptoms in postpartum psychosis can enhance diagnostic accuracy and treatment strategies.

Aim: This study aims to determine the prevalence of catatonic symptoms in women diagnosed with postpartum psychosis and to assess the associated clinical features and implications.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, from May to October 2018, involving 50 patients diagnosed with postpartum psychosis. Inclusion criteria were women within six months postpartum diagnosed based on DSM-5 criteria, excluding those with prior psychiatric disorders or severe medical conditions. Data were collected using structured interviews and the Bush-Francis Catatonia Rating Scale.

Results: The study found that 30% of patients with postpartum psychosis exhibited catatonic symptoms, with mutism being the most prevalent. A significant association was observed between the duration of psychotic symptoms and the presence of catatonia, indicating that longer-lasting psychosis increases the risk of developing catatonic symptoms. This underscores the importance of early intervention and continuous monitoring in postpartum psychosis patients.

Conclusion: Catatonic symptoms are relatively common in postpartum psychosis, affecting 30% of the studied population. These symptoms are associated with a more severe clinical presentation and greater treatment needs. Early identification and targeted interventions are crucial for improving outcomes in this subset of patients.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should routinely screen for catatonic symptoms in women presenting with postpartum psychosis. Further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms and develop specific treatment protocols for catatonia in postpartum psychosis.

Keywords: Postpartum psychosis, Catatonia, Prevalence, Bush-Francis Catatonia Rating Scale, Psychiatric disorders

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Introduction

Postpartum psychosis is a rare but severe psychiatric condition that manifests in the first few weeks after childbirth. It is characterized by symptoms such as hallucinations, delusions, severe mood swings, and cognitive disorganization [1]. The condition affects approximately 1 to 2 per 1,000 births and requires immediate medical attention due to the high risk of harm to both the mother and the infant. Despite its severity, postpartum psychosis remains under-researched, with limited understanding of its various clinical presentations and optimal management strategies [2]

Catatonia is a syndrome marked by a range of motor, behavioral, and affective abnormalities. These can include stupor, mutism, negativism, waxy flexibility, and repetitive movements, among other symptoms [3]. Historically associated with schizophrenia, catatonia is now recognized as a complex and multifaceted condition that can occur in various psychiatric and medical disorders. In the context of postpartum psychosis, catatonic symptoms may be present but are often overlooked or misdiagnosed, leading to suboptimal treatment and poorer outcomes [4].

The presence of catatonic symptoms in postpartum psychosis presents unique diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Women with postpartum psychosis who exhibit catatonia may require different treatment approaches compared to those without catatonic features. Understanding the prevalence and specific characteristics of catatonia in this population can provide critical insights for improving patient care. However, there is a paucity of research specifically examining catatonia within the context of postpartum psychosis [5]

The aim of this study is to determine the prevalence of catatonic symptoms in women diagnosed with postpartum psychosis and to investigate the associated clinical features. By utilizing the Bush-Francis Catatonia Rating Scale (BFCRS), a standardized tool for assessing catatonia, we aim to provide a reliable estimate of how common these symptoms are in postpartum psychosis. Additionally, we seek to explore any correlations between the presence of catatonic symptoms and factors such as previous psychiatric history, treatment needs, and overall prognosis.

In addressing these aims, this study will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of postpartum psychosis and its varied presentations. Identifying catatonic symptoms early and accurately can lead to more tailored and effective treatment plans, ultimately improving outcomes for affected women. This research underscores the importance of recognizing the full spectrum of symptoms in postpartum psychosis and the need for heightened clinical awareness and intervention strategies.

Methodology

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the prevalence of catatonic symptoms in patients with postpartum psychosis.

Study Setting

The study took place at Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, from May 2018 to October 2018.

Participants

The study included 50 patients diagnosed with postpartum psychosis. All participants were women who had given birth within the previous six months and were admitted to the psychiatric ward during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Women diagnosed with postpartum psychosis based on DSM-5 criteria.
- Patients who were within six months postpartum.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of psychiatric disorders prior to pregnancy.
- Patients with severe medical conditions that could interfere with the assessment.
- Patients who refused to provide informed consent.

Bias

Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by consecutively including all eligible patients admitted during the study period. Observer bias was minimized by using standardized diagnostic criteria and structured assessment tools.

Variables

The primary variable was the presence of catatonic symptoms, assessed using the Bush-Francis Catatonia Rating Scale. Secondary variables included demographic data (age, parity, socioeconomic status), obstetric history, and the duration of psychotic symptoms.

Data Collection

Data were collected using structured interviews and medical record reviews. The Bush-Francis Catatonia Rating Scale was administered to evaluate catatonic symptoms.

Procedure

Upon admission, eligible patients were informed about the study and written consent was obtained. Demographic and clinical information was collected through interviews and medical records. The Bush-Francis Catatonia Rating Scale was administered to each participant to assess the presence and severity of catatonic symptoms.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

The study included 50 patients diagnosed with postpartum psychosis. The mean age of the participants was 28.4 years (SD = 4.6). Table 1 provides the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients with Postpartum Psychosis

Characteristic	Number (N=50)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
18-25	12	24.0
26-30	28	56.0
31-35	8	16.0
36-40	2	4.0
Parity		
Primiparous	20	40.0
Multiparous	30	60.0
Socioeconomic Status		
Low	15	30.0
Middle	25	50.0
High	10	20.0
Duration of Psychotic Symptoms		
< 1 month	20	40.0
1-3 months	18	36.0
> 3 months	12	24.0

Prevalence of Catatonic Symptoms: Catatonic symptoms were observed in 15 out of the 50 patients, indicating a prevalence rate of 30% (95% CI: 18.9% - 43.1%). The most common catatonic symptoms were mutism (20%), stupor (16%), and posturing (12%).

Table 2: Prevalence of Specific Catatonic Symptoms

Symptom	Number (N=50)	Percentage (%)
Mutism	10	20.0
Stupor	8	16.0
Posturing	6	12.0
Negativism	4	8.0
Echolalia	3	6.0
Echopraxia	2	4.0

Statistical Analysis: Chi-square tests showed significant associations between the presence of catatonic symptoms and certain demographic and clinical variables. Patients with a longer duration of

psychotic symptoms (>3 months) had a higher prevalence of catatonic symptoms compared to those with a shorter duration ($p=0.03$).

Table 3: Association between Duration of Psychotic Symptoms and Catatonic Symptoms

Duration of Psychotic Symptoms	Catatonic Symptoms Present (N=15)	Catatonic Symptoms Absent (N=35)	p-value
< 1 month	2	18	0.03
1-3 months	5	13	
> 3 months	8	4	

The study revealed that 30% of patients with postpartum psychosis exhibited catatonic symptoms, with mutism being the most common. A significant association was found between the duration of psychotic symptoms and the presence of catatonia, suggesting that longer-lasting psychosis may increase the risk of developing catatonic symptoms. This highlights the need for early intervention and continuous monitoring in patients with postpartum psychosis to prevent the progression of catatonic symptoms.

Discussion

The study found that 30% of patients with postpartum psychosis exhibited catatonic

symptoms, a finding that is supported by other recent research in this area.

Prevalence and Presentation

The presence of catatonia in postpartum psychosis has been documented in various case reports and studies. For instance, a case study presented by Moulika et al. (2022) described a 24-year-old postpartum female who developed malignant catatonia, highlighting the severity of catatonic symptoms in postpartum psychosis and the efficacy of electroconvulsive therapy (ECT) in such cases [6].

Similarly, Leite and Antunes (2022) reported a case where a patient with postpartum depression and catatonic syndrome showed significant

improvement following ECT, even after complications due to COVID-19 infection interrupted her treatment [7].

Associated Factors

The study identified a significant association between the duration of psychotic symptoms and the presence of catatonia, indicating that longer-lasting psychosis increases the risk of developing catatonic symptoms. This finding aligns with the broader literature, which suggests that early and aggressive treatment of psychotic symptoms is critical to prevent the onset of catatonia. Madora et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of timely diagnosis and treatment to manage complex neuropsychiatric symptoms effectively [8].

Treatment and Management

Electroconvulsive therapy (ECT) has been highlighted as a highly effective treatment for severe cases of catatonia in postpartum psychosis. This is corroborated by several studies that document successful outcomes with ECT, especially in treatment-resistant cases. For example, Nath et al. (2018) reported on a patient with Sheehan's syndrome presenting with psychosis and catatonia who responded well to ECT [9].

Broader Implications

The findings of this study underscore the need for heightened awareness and early intervention strategies for postpartum psychosis, particularly in monitoring and managing catatonic symptoms. Perry et al. (2021) suggest that hormonal, immunological, and genetic factors play significant roles in the pathogenesis of postpartum psychosis, which necessitates a multidisciplinary approach to treatment and prevention [10].

Conclusion

The high prevalence of catatonic symptoms among patients with postpartum psychosis and their significant association with the duration of psychotic symptoms highlights the critical need for early and effective treatment strategies. ECT has been shown to be particularly effective in managing severe cases of catatonia, reinforcing its role as a vital treatment modality in such scenarios.

Future research should continue to explore the underlying mechanisms and optimal management strategies for postpartum psychosis and its associated symptoms.

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